

Search for New Anthelmintics—Part I. Synthesis on Some N¹-(Arylaminothiocarbonyl- thioacetyl)-N³-aryl Ureas

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THIRTY new N¹-(arylaminothiocarbonylthioacetyl)-N³-aryl ureas have been synthesized by condensing the ammonium salt of various dithiocarbamic acids with chloroacetyl ureas in aqueous acetone. Nine of these compounds have been screened against *H. nana* and *N. brasiliensis* infections in rats.

Esters of dithiocarbamic acids have clearly been established as the leading anthelmintics¹⁻². A large number of urea derivatives have appeared in recent literature as potent anthelmintics³⁻⁵. Hence the synthesis of title ureas was undertaken.

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected. Substituted phenyl ureas were prepared by treating an appropriate amine with a solution of potassium cyanate according to the method of Berlinerblau⁶. 1-Chloroacetyl-3-arylureas were prepared by the

method of Jacob *et al*⁷. Ammonium salts of various dithiocarbamic acids were prepared by following a published procedure⁸.

N¹-(Arylaminothiocarbonylthioacetyl)-N³-aryl ureas :

1-Chloroacetyl-3-aryl urea (0.01 mole) and an appropriate ammonium dithiocarbamate (0.01 mole) were dissolved in 100 ml of aqueous acetone and the mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 3 hrs. The acetone was then distilled off, and the crude solid obtained was washed with cold water and recrystallised from acetone (Table 1). All the compounds showed consistent nitrogen analyses.

Bio-assay :

Nine compounds numbered 1, 3, 4, 8, 9, 10, 15, 20, 21 (Table 1) have been screened against *H. nana* and *N. brasiliensis* infection in rats, according to the method of Whitlock¹⁰. These compounds were administered orally at a dose of 250 mg/Kg × 1 in case of *H. nana* and 250 mg/Kg × 3 in case of *N. brasiliensis*. None of them, however, showed any significant activity.

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TABLE I

Sl. No.	RC ₆ H ₄ NHC(=S)SCH ₂ CONHCONHC ₆ H ₄ R'		M.P. °C	Yield %
	R	R'		
1.	H	4-OCH ₃	141	72
2.	H	4-Cl	140	75
3.	2-CH ₃	3-CH ₃	139	73
4.	2-CH ₃	4-OCH ₃	134	74
5.	2-CH ₃	2-Cl	133	68
6.	2-CH ₃	4-Cl	185	74
7.	3-CH ₃	2-CH ₃	105	80
8.	3-CH ₃	3-CH ₃	110	71
9.	3-CH ₃	4-CH ₃	160	72
10.	3-CH ₃	2-OCH ₃	132	70
11.	3-CH ₃	2-Cl	143	72
12.	3-CH ₃	4-Cl	140	70
13.	4-CH ₃	3-CH ₃	129	72
14.	4-CH ₃	4-Cl	132	80
15.	2-OCH ₃	3-CH ₃	135	69
16.	2-OCH ₃	4-CH ₃	127	80
17.	2-OCH ₃	2-Cl	130	72
18.	2-OCH ₃	4-Cl	133	72
19.	4-OCH ₃	2-CH ₃	140	71
20.	4-OCH ₃	4-CH ₃	135	68
21.	4-OCH ₃	2-OCH ₃	132	68
22.	4-OCH ₃	2-Cl	134	70
23.	4-OCH ₃	4-Cl	135	72
24.	3-Cl	H	144	73
25.	3-Cl	4-CH ₃	133	79
26.	3-Cl	2-OCH ₃	134	71
27.	3-Cl	4-Cl	148	70
28.	4-Cl	H	130	74
29.	4-Cl	4-CH ₃	145	70
30.	4-Cl	4-Cl	135	68

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